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ELCHIN'S PERSPECTIVES ON LITERARY CRITICISM

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Abstract

The aim of the article is to clarify Elchin's literary-critical ideas as a professional critic. Elchin is also known as a writer in the literary process. Therefore, there is an approach to his activity from the position of writerly criticism. This does not reflect the truth. Such approaches contradict the essence of objective criticism. Because his scientific-theoretical conclusions distance him from writerly criticism. The critical ideas in his research correspond to the essence of professional criticism. This approach, critical judgment also forms the basis of his artistic creativity. He approached social phenomena from an objective aspect, discovered both beauty and negative aspects, and was able to reveal them, touching upon vivid events that make the reader think. The sense of responsibility in his artistic creativity has equally continued in his scientific activity. At the junction of artistic thought and critical thought, the personality of a writer and critic has been formed.

In Elchin's monographs and articles, the creative and methodological issues of Azerbaijani literary criticism, the tasks of modern criticism, the current problems of the literary process, the development directions of the history of criticism and its aesthetic features, and the potential possibilities of Azerbaijani literary criticism have been the object of research. He should take his place as a professional critic among critics such as Mirza Fatali Akhundzade, Kamal Talibzadeh, Mikayil Rafili, Gasim Gasimzade, Mammad Jafar Jafarov, Mammad Arif Dadashzade, Yashar Garayev, Masud Alioglu, Akbar Aghayev, Qulu Khalilov, Bakir Nabiyev. The scholar, who involves both criticism and prose in mutual research, has drawn attention to the importance of critical thought in the development of prose, and issues such as modernity, tradition and innovation, and character have been revealed in the dialectical unity of criticism and prose. The critic, who gives importance to the study of modern and classical heritage, has not left aside the problem of historicism and modernity in literature.

As a result, we conclude that Elchin holds the view that literary criticism is an expression of professionalism. The critic has based his work on methodological principles.

Keywords: criticism, professional critic, modernity, literary process, prose

Introduction. Thought, freedom, responsibility, and objectivity - these are essential elements in all areas of literature and literary studies. However, in literary criticism, the attainment of these concepts as independent principles is particularly significant in terms of addressing the assigned topic and problematics. Debate surrounding the question, "Can criticism that activates thought and demonstrates creative principledness fulfill its duties?" continues to prevail within the literary process. The primary reason for this lies in the responsible approach to intellectual freedom. The existence of criticism is only possible through the critic's freedom of thought. Unfortunately, it must be noted that representatives of writerly criticism and professional criticism have often prioritized ideology over free thought. "Rather than offering an escape from ideology, then, literary texts may be considered as places where the structures and fractures of ideology are both produced and reproduced. Literary texts do not simply or passively "express" or reflect the ideology of their particular time and place. Rather, they are sites of conflict and difference, places where values and preconceptions, beliefs and prejudices, knowledge and social structures are represented and, in the process, opened to

transformation" (Andrew, B.; Nicholas R, 2004, p.177).

In fact, ideology represents a starting path for development. It embodies a system of shared ideas, common convictions, and collective values. Whether in politics or in artistic creation, it serves the purpose of directing consciousness and preserving beliefs. Ideology has always existed in literature; however, its most prominent manifestation falls within the Soviet period. If we examine the historical stages from the twentieth century to the contemporary era, we observe that in literary criticism the early decades of the century were dominated by the ideology of nationalism, the period from the 1920s to the 1990s by socialist ideology, and the years of independence by liberal ideology.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, the confrontation of ideologies was manifested in the example of the journals "Molla Nasreddin" and "Füyuzat". In Soviet literary criticism, the presence of persuasion, the subordination of the primary objective to collective psychological equilibrium, and the legitimization of the dominant worldview demonstrate that criticism remained faithful to a regime of ideological monism within political consciousness.

However, it is also a fact that the most active period of Azerbaijani literary criticism is associated with Soviet literature. In a period when ideology was dominant, professional criticism occupied a leading position. Elchin is a figure in critical thought who serves a liberal ideology. His criticism is fundamentally grounded in free thought.

Literary criticism, one of the important branches of literary studies, has the capacity to influence the activity of creative personalities and to shape aesthetic taste. This, in turn, is a dimension that serves the development of artistic creativity. Moving away from descriptive articles and orienting itself toward objective evaluation, the primary task of criticism is to approach literary works from the standpoint of scientific values. The ability to penetrate the depths of the psychology of creativity is an essential factor for a critic. The quality of criticism depends on the level of justification of the evaluation given to the analyzed work. Just as the concept of criticism is a leading feature in various spheres of society, in literary studies professional criticism must also maintain its dominant position. In this regard, the distinction between writerly criticism and professional criticism emerges as a defining feature. In certain cases, literary figures, through their creative work and scientific-theoretical conclusions, embody both the writer and the critic within their personality. Among such figures, the creative activity of Mirza Fatali Akhundzade, Seyid Huseyn, Mir Jalal Pashayev, Mehdi Huseyn, Mirza Ibrahimov, and Elchin may be noted. The primary target audience of both the author of a literary work and the researcher evaluating that work is the readership. Therefore, their activity is oriented toward a single purpose: guiding the aesthetic taste of the reader in artistic creativity toward aesthetic criteria and combining aesthetic judgment in critical thought with critical reflection.

In the analysis of a work, a writer, creative activity, and critical ideas, the presence of methodological precision creates conditions for the development of criticism and for the literary process to continue in a proper direction. Hesitation and the weakness of polemical force make it difficult to establish standards and criteria. Vaqif Yusifli has clarified the question of what kind of critic Elchin is as follows: "Although Elchin's polemics sometimes attract attention in a harsh and excessive manner, they are free from personal bias, gossip, and malicious intent. And, most importantly, he substantiates his ideas and opinions with sufficient theoretical preparation and a critical way of thinking" (Yusifli V., 1999, p.227).

Elchin has succeeded in providing a methodological approach to the systematic solution of the problems raised in his criticism. In his research work "Criticism and Prose", while studying the relationship of literary criticism of the years 1945–1965 with prose, he did not follow a chronological method; instead, he traced the literary process through its problematic issues. Although he did not conduct a strict periodization, the study, in terms of its thematic structure, addresses interrelated and successive issues. In the introduction of his research, Elchin provides information about his methodological mastery and

explains the scientific-logical approach underlying the problems he raises. Elchin's criticism is distinguished by its conceptual nature. In his approach to prose within criticism, he addresses the problems of modernity and character from the standpoint of tradition and innovation. The critic, who writes that "Where there is no modernity, there is no art" (Elchin, 2005, p.228), analyzes the logical implications of these ideas and interprets them, directing his thought toward the formation of new ideas.

In literary works, it is relatively easy to clarify the degree to which the category of modernity is employed. A critic's ability to comprehend this concept, to introduce a work into the literary process, and to adopt a specific critical position toward it remains an issue of enduring relevance in all periods. Regardless of whether works are written about the recent or distant past, those that are required by present generations, that respond to contemporary demands, and that serve the future development and interests of humanity constitute the core of the content of the category of modernity. In other words, the concept of modernity encompasses not only contemporary writers but also writers of past and ancient periods who carry a modern spirit. Modernity is not limited to literary works alone; it is also related to the critic's ability to perceive the present time and to possess a deeply reflective literary-critical mind. "Criticism is always contemporary and always serves modernity. In the influence that modernity exerts on moral and spiritual quests, the moral value, impact, and authority of criticism itself are expressed. In every period, criticism assumes responsibility for the moral perfection of the reader and of art as a whole. The work performed by criticism as an act of artistic-aesthetic consciousness, as the 'moral conscience' of art, consists precisely in this function. Life becomes aware of itself in art, and art becomes aware of itself in criticism" (Garayev Y., 1981, p.186).

In Elchin's analyses, there is a clear attempt to elucidate the manner in which criticism approaches modernity. The quality of modernity in Elchin's work requires an innovative attitude from the critic toward reality and creativity. The novelty of criticism also depends on the quality of the literary material. Elchin has also not overlooked the influence of those who indulge in superficial literary attitudes or prefer a "telegraphic style" within the literary process. "The main significance of art consists in reflecting what is of interest to human existence. However, while being interested in the phenomena of life, a person cannot, consciously or unconsciously, avoid passing judgment on these phenomena. A writer or artist, as a human being, cannot avoid judging the phenomena being depicted" (Chernyshevsky N., 1956, p.128).

The existence of characters who carry the aesthetic ideal of an epoch, embody progressive ideas, and are capable of making them comprehensible may guide criticism itself. Criticism is not a one-sided process; its foundation, methodological inquiry, and aesthetic problems are formed on the basis of literary material and the critic's individual style. It is also the literary material that brings an innovative spirit to the critic. A work that corresponds to life, as well as its analysis,

shapes the category of modernity. Elchin noted that “the reader wanted to see in the works they read the artistic-philosophical reflection of innovations and development in life, and their interpretation at the same level - if it is a work of art, in an artistic form; if it is a sample of literary criticism, in a scientific-philosophical form” (Elchin, 2005, p.170).

A critic is a reader who possesses scientific knowledge, the capacity for philosophical generalization, and the responsibility of evaluation. However, unlike that of an ordinary reader, his assessment is not the product of initial impression or subjective judgment; rather, it is the result of free thought that connects artistic truth with the contemporary era. In Elchin’s studies, this line of thought is directed toward analytical investigation based on facts. In other words, he is not a descriptive critic but an applicative one. Thus, when contrasting the concepts of national tradition and literary tradition, he refers to Ilyas Afandiyev’s work “The Bridge Builders”. Elchin wrote: “National tradition and literary tradition are not identical; although national tradition and literary tradition form a unity, in certain cases they may not coincide. Literary tradition may develop in the opposite direction to national tradition and, as a result, may, over the course of years, contribute to the disappearance of that national tradition. National tradition may develop in opposition to an artificial literary tradition and, consequently, after many years, lead to the elimination and disappearance of that literary tradition” (Elchin, 2005, p.173).

In addressing how criticism responds to a new theme introduced into literature beyond national tradition, he sometimes adopts a hesitant stance, sometimes a courageous one, and at other times challenges subjective views by emphasizing the dynamism of artistic creativity and its openness to innovation: “In contrast to the progressive position of Azerbaijani prose, literary criticism acted from a conservative, and at times even regressive, position” (Elchin, 2005, p.165).

In order to preserve objectivity, the critic must free himself from archaic modes of thinking within his consciousness. In his view, tradition and innovation, although seemingly opposed to one another, do not negate each other; rather, they exist in a dialectical unity in all periods in the name of modernity. “True modernity can be revealed and studied through understanding ‘what’, that is, what kind of life content is reflected in ‘how’, through examining the relationship between ‘what’ and ‘how’, and through perceiving their harmony” (Mammadov, M., 1968, p.9).

The main characteristic of the category of modernity is connected with the system of artistic images, the typical conditions of unfolding events, the character features of images, and issues of content and form - in short, with the artistic mastery of the literary work. Regarding the issue of character, Elchin’s response to the question “What should criticism be like?” is grounded in the existence of critics capable of escaping the grip of ideology and breaking the silence. A critic should not merely analyze the opposition

between positive and negative characters; rather, he should demonstrate the competence to express his own attitude toward the writer’s characters. “The strength of an artistic image lies in its emotionality and in its possession of aesthetic content. An artistic image is such an aesthetic map in which objective and subjective, particular and general, individual and typical, emotional and rational aspects are firmly and organically united” (Mammadov M., 1975, p.103). In literary evaluation, forgetting the emotional dimension of the literary work and taking sides between positive and negative characters within the author’s conceptual framework also affects the quality of objective criticism itself.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, Mammad Said Ordubadi opposed those who propagated the idea that “there is no criticism, and poetry and literature should be left to the decree of fate,” and he argued: “Our criticism, for the time being, does not possess the inclination toward free thought, independent reflection, and providing literature with an autonomous direction. In the spirit of our criticism, the influence of individual personalities occupies a greater place than the artistic impact of the work to be criticized” (Ordubadi M.S., 1967, p.357). If we turn our attention to the contemporary period, controversial opinions regarding the failure of criticism to fulfill its functions still prevail. On this issue, Elchin stated: “There is Azerbaijani literary criticism, about which complaints are heard; its level and condition cause concern for some” (Yusifli V., Yusifli C., 1999, p.215).

Thus, expectations regarding criticism have always existed and will continue to exist, because the application of theoretical thought in the literary process is not uniform. Criticism develops along a historical trajectory, while attention to theoretical and practical aspects is often pushed into the background. Criticism becomes a tool that deliberately sacrifices its modernity to historicism and subordinates the evaluative thought derived from the quality of the literary work to the status of the writer. Criticism exists, yet its essence has changed. Critics exist, yet critical erudition remains weak. The critic’s anxiety noted by Yaşar Garayev, the critic’s responsibility advocated by Elchin, and the realization of the critic’s freedom that we demand will ensure the development of criticism on its proper foundations.

A distinctive feature characterizing Elchin’s style is the figurative expression of thought. This mode of expression serves to convey ideas in a vivid and dynamic manner within scholarly discourse. Aesthetic value is a driving force of criticism; therefore, such a style influences aesthetic perception and ensures that ideas are more easily retained in memory. In the critic’s formulations, the research objective is presented in a fully vivid manner, while emotional nuance is intensified. Such an analytical approach aims both to stimulate thought and to evoke emotional response. A function of concentration is also evident. Using metaphor, he compares the formation of a literary work to the development of a tree: “A tree itself is a literary work. It has countless branches, large and small: the laws, genres, style, form, architectonics, structure of

literature; the idea, philosophical, aesthetic, and ethical concepts served by the writer; his worldview, position, writing culture, artistic mastery, and so on. On these branches there are various delicate leaves: features that make the literary work aesthetically refined and intellectually meaningful. However, both these branches and leaves rest upon the trunk, which is their support and source of nourishment. The roots are talent. The roots absorb nourishment from the soil. The soil is life, and nourishment is themes" (Elchin., 2005, p.228). This feature does not merely characterize the individuality of his expressive style; rather, it demonstrates that the critic's manner of writing stems from the methodology of criticism itself.

Conclusion. By examining Elchin's position in the literary process and his creative qualities as a figure who develops contemporary critical thought from a methodological perspective, the differences between writerly criticism and professional criticism have been brought to light. The methodology in Elchin's criticism is subordinated to the general principles of literary criticism. At the same time, through his critical ideas, he has revealed his individual creative qualities. The writer embodies two interconnected characteristics within the Azerbaijani literary process: that of a writer and that of a professional critic. In his artistic creativity, critical judgment is also present. This is precisely the feature that characterizes his criticism. In other words, this talent is dominant throughout his overall creative output. In his literary works, artistic expression is fundamental, whereas in his critical ideas, scientific-theoretical thought constitutes the main basis. Elchin is among the critics who continue, in the contemporary

period, the tradition of the professional school of literary criticism that began with Mirza Fatali Akhundzade. What distinguishes him from other critics is his adherence to the concept of modernity in criticism. His attempt to define the differences between literary tradition and national tradition is directed toward clarifying the concept of modernity. At the same time, his analyses have the capacity to guide the literary process, while critical reflection possesses the power to shape public opinion.

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